

MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES OF TEACHERS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS IN THE DIVISION OF OLONGAPO CITY

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Multiple Intelligences of Teachers and Academic Performance of Pupils in the Division of Olongapo City

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Abstract

This study investigated the correlation between teachers' multiple intelligences and pupils' Language Assessment for Primary Grades (LAPG) performance in selected elementary schools in Olongapo City during SY 2017-2018. A descriptive research design was employed, involving 138 Grade IV teachers as respondents. Data was collected through questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that most teachers assessed themselves as having verbal-linguistic intelligence (26.8%), followed by interpersonal intelligence (24.6%). Pupils achieved a "near mastery" level on the LAPG. Significant differences in teachers' multiple intelligences were observed based on educational qualification and years of service. A weak but significant positive correlation ($r=0.173$, $p<0.05$) was found between teachers' logical-mathematical intelligence and pupils' LAPG scores. The study was limited to Grade IV teachers and pupils in Olongapo City, potentially affecting generalizability. The findings suggest that teachers' multiple intelligences, particularly logical-mathematical intelligence, may influence pupils' language assessment performance. This implies the need for considering multiple intelligences in teacher hiring, development, and instructional strategies to potentially enhance student outcomes.

Keywords: *language assessment, multiple intelligences, primary education, teacher characteristics, teaching effectiveness*

Introduction

Intelligence has traditionally been viewed as a single, measurable cognitive capacity that individuals are born with. However, Howard Gardner's theory of Multiple Intelligences (MI), proposed in 1983, challenged this notion by suggesting that humans possess multiple distinct intelligences that can be developed (Gardner, 1983). Gardner initially identified seven intelligences: linguistic, logical-mathematical, musical, bodily-kinesthetic, spatial, interpersonal, and intrapersonal. He later added naturalist intelligence and considered adding existential intelligence (Gardner, 1999). The MI theory posits that individuals have unique profiles across these intelligences and can improve in different areas. This contrasts with traditional views of intelligence as fixed and primarily based on linguistic and logical-mathematical abilities (Thirteen, 2004).

Gardner's theory has been embraced by many educators as it resonates with their observations of how students learn differently. It provides a framework for understanding diverse student abilities and developing varied instructional approaches (Thirteen, 2004). However, some critics argue that Gardner's "intelligence" are simply talents or skills rather than true intelligence (Morgan, 1996; Traub, 1998). The theory has also been criticized for lacking strong empirical support and being based more on Gardner's intuition (Waterhouse, 2006). Despite these critiques, MI theory has gained significant traction in educational settings. Applying MI theory in classrooms allows teachers to better recognize students' varied strengths and learning styles. It encourages the development of diverse teaching methods to engage different intelligences (Martinez, 2005). The theory can also be useful in workplace settings by helping form effective teams and allowing individuals to leverage their intellectual strengths (Piotrowski, 2009). Understanding employees' MI profiles can improve team dynamics, morale, and performance (Capotosto, 2005; Quah, 2010).

Several studies have examined relationships between multiple intelligences and various outcomes. Research has explored connections between MI profiles and language proficiency, academic performance, and teaching effectiveness. Some studies have found correlations between certain intelligence and specific skills or outcomes, while others have not identified significant relationships (Saricaoglu & Arikan, 2009; Razmjoo, 2008; D'Acosta, 2000). The mixed findings highlight the need for further research on how multiple intelligences relate to educational and professional outcomes.

This study aims to investigate the multiple intelligences of teachers and their relationship to student academic performance, specifically Language Assessment for Primary Grades (LAPG) scores. By examining these connections, the research seeks to provide insights that could inform teaching practices and professional development. Understanding how teachers' MI profiles may influence student outcomes could help optimize instructional approaches and improve educational effectiveness. The conceptual framework for this study includes teachers' demographic profiles and multiple intelligence scores as independent variables, with students' LAPG performance as the dependent variable.

The research utilizes the Multiple Intelligences for Adult Literacy and Education (MIALE) inventory developed by Dr. Terry Armstrong to assess teachers' MI profiles across the eight established intelligences. By analyzing relationships between these variables, the study aims to contribute to the body of knowledge on multiple intelligences in educational settings and their potential impacts on student achievement.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to examine the multiple intelligences of teachers and academic performance of pupils in the Division of Olongapo City, Philippines. Descriptive research aims to describe and interpret existing conditions, relationships, practices, beliefs, and trends (Goods & Scates, 2003). This approach was deemed appropriate for investigating the varied MI profiles among teachers and potential connections to student outcomes. The study participants included all Grade IV teachers in the Division of Olongapo City, totaling 138 teachers across 28 elementary schools. This comprehensive sampling of Grade IV teachers in the division aimed to provide a representative picture of MI profiles among this group of educators. Data collection utilized a questionnaire as the primary instrument. The questionnaire consisted of two main sections: 1) demographic information including age, sex, educational qualifications, specializations, and years of teaching experience, and 2) the Multiple Intelligences for Adult Literacy and Education (MIALE) inventory created by Dr. Terry Armstrong. The MIALE assesses individuals across the eight established multiple intelligences through a series of self-report items.

To ensure proper data collection, the researcher obtained necessary permissions from the Schools Division Office of Olongapo City and individual school principals. Questionnaires were then administered to participating teachers, who were given adequate time to complete the self-assessment. Student LAPG scores were also collected as a measure of academic performance. Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage distribution, and weighted means, were used to summarize teacher profiles and MI scores. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and t-tests for independent samples were employed to examine potential differences in MI scores based on teacher demographic variables. Pearson correlation analysis was used to investigate relationships between teachers' MI scores and students' LAPG performance. A significance level of 0.05 was used for hypothesis testing. This methodology aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis of Grade IV teachers' MI profiles in Olongapo City and explore potential connections to student academic outcomes. By utilizing established MI assessment tools and rigorous statistical analysis, the study sought to contribute meaningful insights to the understanding of multiple intelligences in educational settings.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the respondents

Age. The data shows that most of the teacher-respondents with 25 or equivalent to 18.10% are under the age range of 41-45 years old; 23 or 16.70%, 31-35 years old; 22 or 15.90%, 36-40 years old; 19 or 13.80% from 26-30 years old; 15 or 10.905 from 51-55 years old; 12 or 8.70% from 56-60 years old; 60 or 4.30% from 20-25 year old and only 2 or equivalent to 1.40% from 61 years old and above. The computed mean age of the teacher respondents was 40.78 years old. The data implies that most of the teacher-respondents were from age group of 41-45 years old and least from 61 years old and above. In Erik Erikson's stages of development, the respondents were classified in their middle adulthood, which ranges from 41-60 years old. This is the stage of a personhood which focus more on career or job development, family and economic stability. This further shows that the teacher-respondents are enjoying their teaching profession (Espiritu, 1985).

Sex. Out of one hundred thirty-eight (138) teacher-respondents, the majority with 128 or equivalent to 92.80%, are females, and 10 or equivalent to 7.20% are males. The study shows that female teachers are more compassionate and demonstrate motherly like to the children. Similarly, in the study of Akiri (2014) as cited by Corpuz (2016) that female teachers are more satisfied in the teaching career than males.

Educational Attainment. Out of one hundred thirty-eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 69, or equivalent to 50.00% who are college graduates; 60, or 43.50%, have attended master units of education, and 9 or equivalent to 6.50% are considered as full pledge master graduates. The data further reveals on the importance of graduate education studies as part of their professional advancement. The activity of teaching is very critical in the teaching and learning process, which requires a maximum level of development of teaching and communication skills of the teacher. The data further implies on the need to upgrade the educational qualifications of the teachers since there is a mandate by the Professional Regulatory Commission regarding the renewal of licensed for teachers to undergo continuing professional development (CPD). The teachers with sufficient academic preparation are seen to be competent in subject matter content and pedagogical skills enabling them to be effective in classroom and produce larger student achievement gains (Darling-Hammond, 2000).

Specializations. Out of one hundred and thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 26 or equivalent to 18.80% are majors in Mathematics; 35 or 25.40% are English majors; 18 or 13.005 are Filipino majors; 16 or 11.60% are Science majors; 9 or 6.50% are majors in Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao; 7 or 5.10% are majors in Edukasyon sa Pangkabuhayan at Pantahanan; 14 or equivalent to 10.10% are majors in Araling Panlipunan and 13 or equivalent to 9.40% are majors in Music, Arts, PE and Health. Clearly gleaned from the table that most of the teacher-respondents are majors in English. According to the teacher-respondents, preference to take English as major subject for it is considered as the universal language subject. Noted only few taking majors like Edukasyon Pangkabuhayan at Pantahanan where the subject is considered not challenging though it is more practical and useful in life.

Years of Service. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 39 or equivalent to 28.30% had served for 1-

5 years in the teaching profession; 16 or 11.60% with 6-10 years in the service; 10 or 7.20%, 11-15 years in the service; 19 or 13.80%, 16-20 years in the service; 11 or 8.00%, 21-25 years in the service; 8 or 5.80%, 26-30 years in the service; 1 or 0.70%, 31-35 years and 34 or equivalent to 24.60% had served for 36-40 years in teaching. The computed mean years of teaching service was 18.25 years. The data clearly implies on the dedication of the teacher-respondents to the teaching profession. They have already spent their productive years in teaching. According to them, they had no more plan to change work and are determine to stay in teaching up to the age of retirement. The years of experience are often indicator of teacher quality (Goldhaber and Anthony, 2003).

Multiple Intelligences of the Teacher-Respondents

Verbal-Linguistic. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents there are 37 or equivalent to 26.80 percent assessed themselves with linguistic intelligence. Having this multiple intelligence where manifested to possess the ability of making easy to make stories; find easy to remember quotes and phrases; at school, one of the favorites subject is English; when talking to someone, they tend to listen to the words they use not just what they mean; enjoy cross words, word searches or other word puzzles; enjoy debates and discussions; often talk to self, out loud or in my head; and find it easy to pick up the basics of another language; and find pleasure in reading. This intelligence has to do with words, spoken or written. People with high verbal linguistic intelligence display a facility with words and languages. As to Howard Gardner's Multiple Intelligences Theory, this intelligence has to do with words, spoken or written language. Teachers should be communicative both orally and in written. The role of teacher is to communicate with the students. The message should be clear, accurate and precise.

Logical-Mathematical. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 3 or equivalent to 2.20 percent with logical –mathematical intelligence. The individual with this intelligence find mental arithmetic easy; they like to think through problem carefully, considering all the consequences; find easy to remember telephone numbers; they don't use fingers when counting; their favorite subject is Math; find budgeting and managing my money easy", they do not like ambiguity, and like all things to be made clear; they annoy people behaving irrationally; and like to be systematic and thorough. The Logical –mathematical intelligence pertains to man's capacity to think abstractly, scientifically and critically and people with strong inclination in this intelligence prefer working through patterns and relationships, problem solving, strategic thinking and organizing-skills that incidentally have high utility in the teaching profession, Ronquillo (2011).

Musical. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 12 or equivalent to 8.70 percent with musical intelligence. According to them, they can play a musical instrument; often have a song or piece of music in their head; love Music lesson in the school; have always dreamed of being a musician or singer; singing makes feel happy; find that the music that appeal to me is often based on how I feel emotionally; they like having music on in the background; Music is very important to them; and can identify most sounds without seeing what causes them. Musical intelligence characterize to having sensitivity to sounds, rhythms, tones and music.

Visual-Spatial. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 18 or equivalent to 13.00 percent who demonstrated to have Spatial –visual intelligence. This intelligence find graphs and charts easy to understand, the person can always recognizes places that have been before, even when they were very young; often see clear images when close their eyes; the person can read map easily; if wanted to learn how to do something, I they like to see drawings and diagrams of how it works; their house is full of picture and photographs; and can easily imagine how an object would look from another perspective.

Bodily Kinesthetic. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 16 or equivalent to 11.60 percent who demonstrated to have bodily kinesthetic intelligence. The student possess characteristics of enjoying a sports or dance; love adrenaline sports and scary rides; find ball games easy and enjoyable; find it easiest to solve problems when I am doing something physical; can throw things well-darts, skipping, pebbles, frisbees , etc; they are very tactile person; enjoy and good at making things- with their hands. This intelligence requires to engage more on bodily movement with great stamina to endure the activity. Bodily Kinesthetic refers to the control of one's bodily motions and the capacity to handle objects skillfully.

Interpersonal. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 34 or equivalent to 24.60 percent who demonstrated to have interpersonal multiple intelligence. This intelligence possess characteristic for a person to very social person and like being with other people; can tell easily whether someone likes or dislikes them; can manipulate people if they choose to; they care about how those around them feel; find it easy to talk to new people; very aware of other people's body language; they get upsets to see someone cry and not be able to help; they are good at solving disputes between others; and friends always come to them for emotional support and advice. This intelligence make good in playing team sports which requires ability to interact with other people. The person must be willing to open the line of communication in order to be accepted and be a part of the group. Interpersonal intelligence refers to the ability to interact with others. It is characterized by sensitivity to others' mood, feelings, temperaments, and motivations, and their ability to cooperate in order to work as part of a group.

Intrapersonal. Out of one hundred thirty eight (138) teacher-respondents, there were 7 or equivalent to 5.10 percent who demonstrated to have intrapersonal multiple intelligence. This intelligence make good for a person to enjoy individual sports best; they like to learn more about themselves; they are realistic about personal strengths and weaknesses; they love to keep and write a diary; like to mediate; they are very interested in psychometrics and IQ test; they can predict my feelings and behaviors in certain situations fairly accurately;

”, can set personal goals and plans for the future; and happy spending time alone. Intrapersonal intelligence refers to a deep understanding of the self, assessing personally own strengths, weakness and abilities what a person to be unique and peculiar from the rest and being able to predict own emotions and reactions (Domulot, 2016).

This finding is in contrast with the study of Acosta (2000), as she found that effective teachers displayed high scores in all areas of MI as compared to their average or low effectiveness counterparts. The degree to which they exhibit multiple intelligences was even more profound for interpersonal and logical intelligences. The mean interpersonal intelligences for teachers with low effectiveness was higher than the overall mean interpersonal intelligence. As stated by Sta. Ana (2007), MI provides a way for teachers to reflect upon their teaching methods. It also expands their current teaching repertoire. Furthermore, MI and teaching signify that no one set of strategies would work for all students at all times. The teaching styles of teachers depend on their Multiple Intelligences.

Level of Language Assessment for Primary Grades (LAPG) Performance of the Pupils

There were 10 or equivalent to 7.25% who have obtain a scores of 50 and below which denotes low mastery level; 80 or 57.97 with scores of 51-75 which denotes near mastery and 48 or 34.78% with scores from 75-100 which denotes mastery level. The compute mean of Language Assessment for Primary Grades (LAPG) was 50.25 interpreted as “near mastery” level.

The data clearly manifest that the students obtain a near mastery level and could be ascribed on the effectiveness of teachers in teaching the lesson. It is also accounted on the use of variety of teaching techniques and strategies that makes the lesson meaningful and significant.

The academic progress depends much on how a teacher redirects and redesigns the classroom activities. His knowledge of the different learning styles likewise empowers him to encourage students to explore and go beyond what learning materials tell (Mendoza, 2011). Knowledge of teaching methodologies is essential if one is to be an effective teacher. A teacher who knows a number of teaching methodologies can vary the teaching modes to cater to the varied learning styles of his students. Students who have higher verbal abilities learn effectively if given more verbal-oriented teaching methods. Likewise, those students who are physically active learn effectively if given watch-and-do methodologies. Not all people learn in the same way. Educators must know and understand that learning styles and preferences vary in each individual. (Porado, 2000) , identifies four types of learners : a) those that learn by relating to people b) those that learn by watching and listening c) those that learn by thinking and intellectual understanding and d) those that learn by doing.

Test of Differences on Multiple Intelligences of Teachers when Grouped According to Profile Variables.

Table 1 presents the significant difference of multiple intelligences of teachers when grouped according to profile variables. The computed Significant or P-values of 0.489, 0.691, 0.410 which are higher than ($>$) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, hence there is no significant differences on the multiple intelligences when grouped according to age, sex and specialization. On the other hand, the computed Significant or P-values of 0.037 and 0.000 which are lower than ($<$) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, hence there is significant differences on the multiple intelligences when grouped according to educational qualification and years in the service profile variables respectively.

It can be seen on this table that among the profile variables the highest educational attainment and years in the service show significant differences from the multiple intelligences of teachers. The teacher who are college graduate differ from teachers with master’s units and master’s graduate. The latter appear to exhibit the same level of multiple intelligence.

Table 1. *Analysis of Variance to test differences on the teacher’s multiple intelligences when group according to profile variables*

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	0.368	8	0.046	0.937	0.489	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	6.284	128	0.049			Not Significant
	Total	6.652	136				
Sex	Between Groups	0.008	1	0.008	0.159	0.691	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	6.644	135	0.049			Not Significant
	Total	6.652	136				
Educational Qualification	Between Groups	0.320	2	0.160	3.387	0.037	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	6.331	134	0.047			Significant
	Total	6.652	136				
Specialization	Between Groups	.354	7	0.051	1.036	0.410	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	6.298	129	0.049			Not Significant
	Total	6.652	136				
Years in the Service	Between Groups	4.022	7	0.575	28.190	0.000	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	2.629	129	0.020			Significant
	Total	6.652	136				

This findings contradicts on the study by Menevis and Ozad (2014) found statistical significant differences for gender and verbal, kinesthetic, existential, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalist intelligences. Moreover, same differences were also found for age and visual, logical, intrapersonal, naturalist, and existential intelligences. In the manner, the study of Saricaoglu and Arikan (2009) concluded that there was no significant gender differences in the intelligence types held by the participants except for that between gender and linguistic intelligence which was positive. Negative but significant relationships were found between success in grammar and bodily-kinesthetic, spatial and intrapersonal intelligences. The relationship between musical intelligence and writing was found to be significant and positive. Likewise, Miana-Faunillan (2002) established that secondary school teachers possessed the eight multiple intelligences but bodily-kinesthetic intelligence had the highest mean. Furthermore, she found out that verbal-linguistic, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, intrapersonal and naturalistic-environmental intelligences were not related to all personal variables, namely, age, years of teaching, sex, educational attainment, major subjects, teaching loads, and number of subjects handled.

Relationship between the Multiple Intelligences of the teachers and the LAPG performance of the pupils

The Relationship between the Multiple Intelligences of the teachers and the LAPG performance of the pupils is shown in Table 2. The computed Pearson-r values of 0.104, 0.072, 0.133, 0.067, 0.016, 0.045, and 0.068 which denotes little or weak relationship between the Language Assessment for Primary Grade (LAPG) and the verbal-linguistic, musical-rhythmical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, intrapersonal, interpersonal and naturalist-environmental multiple intelligence of teachers. On the other hand, the computed Pearson r -value of 0.173** which denotes little or weak relationship between the Language Assessment for Primary Grade (LAPG) and the logical-mathematical multiple intelligence. The computed Significant Value of 0.042 which is lower than 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore it is significant.

Table 2. *Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to test relationship between the Languages Assessment for Primary Grades and the Teachers' Multiple Intelligences*

Sources of Correlations		Language Assessment for Primary Grades	Decision
Multiple Intelligences			
Verbal-Linguistic	Pearson Correlation	0.104	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.226	Not Significant
Logical-Mathematical	Pearson Correlation	0.173*	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.042	Significant
Musical-Rhythmical	Pearson Correlation	0.072	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.402	Not Significant
Visual-Spatial	Pearson Correlation	0.133	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.119	Not Significant
Bodily Kinesthetic	Pearson Correlation	0.067	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.435	Not Significant
Interpersonal	Pearson Correlation	0.016	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.853	Not Significant
Intrapersonal	Pearson Correlation	0.045	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.601	Not Significant
Naturalistic- Environmental	Pearson Correlation	0.068	Low Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.431	Not Significant
N		137	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Martinez (2005) also mentioned that teachers need to be familiar with the interests, strengths and weaknesses of the students. By doing so, teachers may develop their lesson plans to include activities that compliments the child's learning intelligence. Also, since multiple intelligences is a foundation for understanding the diverse range of students' abilities, using multiple intelligences in the classroom is extremely important in individualizing of the students' education and not the mass-market education that can be popular in today's schools.

This findings of the study is similar and supports on the study of Ronquillo (2011) primarily circumnavigated on tracing for an existing significant relationship between the eight established multiple intelligences advocated by Howard Gardner and the job performance of Brightwoods School teachers. The results of the study showed that logical-mathematical intelligence had significant relationship to teachers' over-all job performance. To set the record very clearly, this intelligence does not only refer to the human ability on Mathematics but it also pertains to man's capacity to think abstractly, scientifically and critically. Also, people with strong inclination in this intelligence prefer working through patterns and relationships, problem solving, strategic thinking, and organizing- skills that incidentally have high utility in the teaching profession.

The individual with this intelligence find mental arithmetic easy; they like to think through problem carefully, considering all the consequences; find easy to remember telephone numbers; they don't use fingers when counting; their favorite subject is Math; find

budgeting and managing my money easy”, they do not like ambiguity, and like all things to be made clear; they annoy people behaving irrationally; and like to be systematic and thorough (Ronquillo, 2011).

Conclusions

The research concludes that the typical teacher-respondent is a female in early adulthood, a college graduate majoring in English, with nearly two decades of teaching experience. These teachers assessed themselves as having verbal-linguistic multiple intelligence. The pupils were found to be at a "near mastery level" in the Language Assessment for Primary Grade (LAPG). Significant differences in multiple intelligence were observed when grouped according to educational qualification and years of service. Additionally, a weak relationship was found between the pupils' LAPG scores and the teachers' Mathematical-Logical Multiple Intelligence.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. Teachers are encouraged to explore and maximize their intelligences to enhance the teaching and learning process. School administrators should consider assessing the multiple intelligences of teachers during hiring and selection to optimize the contributions of multi-talented individuals to the institution's progress. Furthermore, it is suggested that school administrators conduct in-depth assessments of teachers' multiple intelligences as a basis for assigning additional responsibilities and special duties. Teachers are also urged to identify their respective multiple intelligences to broaden their horizons and develop expertise for improved pupil academic performance. Lastly, it is recommended to conduct a follow-up study with a broader scope to validate and confirm the findings of this research.

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